

Berlin-Brandenburg

BER

This fiche includes maps displaying the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the airport of Berlin (BER) with measurements of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in 2023 (E1a validated data AQ e-Reporting). The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the airport area, location of the SPO in one of the 8 wind sectors around the airport (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), wind frequency blowing from the airport in that WS, population living in the WS within 10 km from the airport, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. This information has been complemented with the EEA air quality annual maps (1 km x 1 km), covering the whole area around the airport and showing in the boxplot the different levels concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region, including the weighted area means for the different land cover classes.

The presented information is based only on SPOs reported to the EEA, additional SPOs or data may exist at national level.

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Airport area and NO₂ air quality SPOs around the airport within 5 and 10 km

Airport area and PM_{2.5} air quality SPOs around the airport within 5, 10 and 20 km

Pozzoli, L., Gerwig, H., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., & Monge, S. (2025). Air quality around airports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2025/7, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17432053>).
[ETC HE Report 2025/7: Air quality around airports — Eionet Portal](#)

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NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Germany	DEBB086	Background	52.35	13.42	8.97		1.96	SW	9.53	13,184
Germany	DEBB112	Background	52.32	13.62	11.27		6.92	SE	7.61	22,519

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PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the airport (Part 1)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Germany	DEBB086	Background	52.35	13.42	8.78	-61.68	1.96	SW	9.53	13,184
Germany	DEBB112	Background	52.32	13.62	8.30		6.92	SE	7.61	22,519
Germany	DEBE069	Traffic	52.44	13.39	11.81		9.69	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE063	Traffic	52.47	13.44	12.26		9.86	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE127	Traffic	52.47	13.44	12.33		9.88	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE056	Background	52.45	13.65	8.22		10.35	NE	21.58	79,387
Germany	DEBE126	Traffic	52.48	13.43	12.31		11.84	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE034	Background	52.49	13.43	10.28	-44.41	12.36	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE034	Background	52.49	13.43	10.92	-44.41	12.36	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE065	Traffic	52.51	13.47	12.15	-47.54	13.97	N	9.91	135,332

PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the airport (Part 2)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Germany	DEBE065	Traffic	52.51	13.47	11.78	-47.54	13.97	N	9.91	135,332
Germany	DEBE061	Traffic	52.46	13.32	10.87		14.88	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE068	Background	52.51	13.42	10.41	-54.36	15.12	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE068	Background	52.51	13.42	10.26	-54.36	15.12	NW	9.92	153,296
Germany	DEBE125	Traffic	52.51	13.38	11.40		15.99	NW	9.92	153,296

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Annual mean NO₂ concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

Pozzoli, L., Gerwig, H., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., & Monge, S. (2025). Air quality around airports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2025/7, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17432053>).
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Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

- High density residential
- Low density residential
- Industry
- Traffic
- Agricultural areas
- Natural areas

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